

Development Of Authentic Assessment Models Of Speaking Skills Elementary School Students In Medan City

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Authentic Assessment, Speaking Skills, Elementary School Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5565002</p>	<p><i>This research is based on problems related to the development of authentic assessments to assess the speaking skills of students who have not used valid, reliable, effective, and practical assessment instruments. The methodology used in the research and development (R&D) Plomp model. The research was carried out in an elementary school in the city of Medan. The resulting product was validated by evaluation experts, material experts, media experts, and education practitioners, then continued with individual tests, small group tests, and large groups. The assessment instrument developed was tested for validity and reliability, testing effectiveness, and testing practicality. The research findings show: (1) mThe authentic assessment model developed is an assessment instrument model to assess students' speaking skills equipped with model books, teacher manuals, and assessment instruments that have been validated for feasibility by educational experts and practitioners, (2) the results of testing the validity of the speaking skills assessment instrument using the Aiken formula and product-moment correlation show that overall the instrument items are valid, (3) the results of the reliability testing of the speaking skills assessment instrument by calculating the interrater reliability coefficient (between raters) obtained the price of the reliability coefficient of 0.82. Furthermore, the results of the reliability test of the speaking skills assessment instrument using the Alpha Cronbach formula showed a reliability coefficient of 0.86. In this case, the reliability coefficients of 0.82 and 0.86 indicate high reliability, (4) mThe authentic assessment model of speaking skills developed is proven to be effective in increasing the achievement of students' speaking skills learning outcomes with the N-Gain coefficient 0.42 moderate category, and (5) the authentic speaking skills assessment model developed has a practical level with a score of 2.92 the practical category needs improvement in the first try and a score of 3.50 very practical category in the second try. The conclusion of the research is an authentic speaking skill assessment model that is developed to be feasible, valid, reliable, effective, and practical to assess students' speaking skills.</i></p>

Introduction

Law Number 20 of 2003 Article 3 concerning the National Education System states that the function of national education is to develop capabilities and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in the context of the intellectual life of the nation. While the aim is to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have a noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens, so that the purpose of education is to National education will be able to create harmony and balance between the dimensions of science and morals in students.

The educational curriculum has changed from time to time, starting from the 1947 curriculum which is called the 1947 lesson plan until now, namely the 2013 curriculum. The current 2013 curriculum is expected to be able to answer the challenges of educational goals in Indonesia. As a new curriculum, the 2013 curriculum has a different direction and paradigm compared to the previous curriculum, namely the 2006 Education Unit Level Curriculum.

Assessment is an integral part of the overall implementation of learning. The position of assessment in learning design is as part of a series of three main components of learning implementation, namely learning objectives, learning activities, and assessment of learning outcomes (Djiwandono, 2011:2). However, in practice in the field, the assessment standards in the 2013 curriculum have not been fully realized, especially in the assessment of language skills. Speaking skills are important for students, both in formal situations and in

building daily communication. Next Atmazaki (2016) revealed that there are several gaps in the implementation of authentic assessments in Indonesian language learning, namely: (1) teachers consider the stages of communicating in a scientific approach as speaking practice; (2) teachers do not use special assessments for speaking skills; (3) teachers focused on assessing reading and writing skills only; (4) teachers have not used authentic assessments to assess students' language skills, and (5) speaking skill assessment is tested only occasionally.

Speaking skills that are rarely tested will make students unable to evaluate their communication skills in public speaking so that the ideas possessed by these students are not conveyed properly. This is evident in the results of research conducted by Nurgiyantoro (2011) as follows: (1) in general, teachers do not understand and have not carried out authentic assessments in language learning in the classroom even though the assessment is one of the ones recommended in the KTSP, (2) teacher empowerment strategies in authentic assessments can be pursued through upgrading, training, and assistance in the practice of making and implementing authentic assessments, and (3) in general, teachers and colleagues hope that the manual contains the concept of authentic assessment, really measures language competence, simple language, easy to follow and there are examples of making assessments and ways the measurement. These three things have a correlation that, in fact, teachers are still confused in using authentic assessments in learning to speak.

One of the reasons why various efforts to improve the quality of education are ineffective is because the planning cycle is too long, implementation is too complex and impractical, causing overload and tiring. Therefore, a simple, but continuous improvement effort is needed. In addition, related to the assessment in the 2013 Curriculum, based on the results of research by Nurgiyantoro (2011), it is known that teachers still have difficulties in conducting assessments. One effort that can be done to solve this problem is to develop an authentic assessment tool for reliable and valid mathematics learning that focuses on the 2013 Curriculum.

The purpose of authentic assessment is to measure various skills in various contexts that reflect real-world situations where these skills are used (Nurgiyantoro, 2011: 23). Authentic assessments can also be used to ensure true information about the abilities or competencies of students. Mueller (2013) mentions that authentic assessment needs to be done for several reasons, namely (1) authentic assessment is a direct assessment of the abilities and competencies of students, (2) authentic assessment provides opportunities for students to construct learning outcomes, (3) authentic assessment integrates learning activities teaching, and assessment, and (4) authentic assessment provides opportunities for students to demonstrate their various abilities.

Based on interviews conducted by researchers with one of the teachers who are members of the working group of elementary school teachers Al Fithriah Medan stated that: (1) teachers have implemented the 2013 Curriculum in schools, but have not followed the assessment standards in the 2013 Curriculum, (2) made assessment tools especially speaking skills, made by the teacher himself without involving other teachers or students, (3) for some assessments of speaking skills the teacher uses the assessments contained in Indonesian language books used in their respective schools and often uses fiction because of the teacher's assumption that they already know the ability of the student.

Based on this explanation, research is needed to develop an authentic speaking skill performance assessment tool. So that teachers can bring students from their modest abilities to their proper abilities. According to Setyosari (2012:217) development research aims to assess changes that occur within a certain time. Not only assessing, but the main goal is to develop a product to meet the criteria and effectiveness gradually.

Assessment is the process of collecting information that can be used to make decisions related to educational policies, quality of education programs, quality of educational programs, quality of the curriculum, quality of learning, or the extent to which knowledge is received by students about teaching materials that have been taught to them (Basuki and Hariyanto, 2015). Furthermore, Anderson and Urquhart (2003:11) explain that assessment is the most important part of the learning process in all fields of study. Assessment is the process of gathering information to make decisions. In other words, assessment in learning is an activity to obtain various information continuously and thoroughly in terms of the process and learning outcomes of students and after participating in learning. The assessment action is closely related to the decision making of the assessment, the more serious the consequences, and implications in the long term. Teachers must be serious about carrying out this assessment. Mueller (2005:1418) explains that authentic assessment can be used as tangible evidence of what students have mastered, in this case, authentic assessments start from personal experience, directly real to students. Furthermore, Majid (2005:178) explains that authentic assessment is an actual assessment of student learning outcomes, in this case not only seeing the final result but the progress of student learning outcomes is assessed from the process. 1418) explains that authentic assessment can be used as real evidence of what students have mastered, in this case, authentic assessments start from personal experience, directly real to students. Furthermore, Majid (2005:178) explains that authentic assessment is an actual assessment of student learning outcomes, in this case not only seeing the final result but the progress of student learning outcomes is assessed from the process. 1418) explains that authentic assessment can be used as real evidence of what students have mastered, in this case, authentic assessments start from personal experience, directly real to

students. Furthermore, Majid (2005:178) explains that authentic assessment is an actual assessment of student learning outcomes, in this case not only seeing the final result but the progress of student learning outcomes is assessed from the process.

Speaking, in general, can be interpreted as conveying one's intentions (ideas, thoughts, hearts) to others by using spoken language so that these intentions can be understood by others. In particular, Tarigan (2008: 15) has stated that speaking is the ability to pronounce articulation sounds or words to express, state, and convey thoughts, ideas, and feelings. Talking is essentially a process of communicating because in it there is a transfer of messages from one source to another.

This development research design uses the Plomp development model. According to Rochmad (2012), the Plomp model is considered suitable for use by undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral students who conduct development research. The Plomp model is considered more flexible and flexible than other development models because at each phase of its activities it can be adapted to the characteristics of the research. This development research uses the Plomp model which is considered more flexible and flexible because each step contains development activities that can be adapted to the characteristics of the research. For example, the preliminary investigation may include preliminary research. Plomp in (Rochmad, 2012) states that: "we characterized educational design in short as a method within which one is working systematically towards the solving of a make" problem." The characteristics of educational design as a method in which people work systematically towards solving the problems created. The Plomp model above consists of a preliminary investigation phase, a design phase, and a realization/construction phase. construction), and the phase of test, evaluation, and revision (test, evaluation, and revision), and implementation (implementation).

METHODS

The research method used is the research and development method or in English, it is called research and development (R&D). According to Sugiyono (2016: 297), research and development methods are research methods used to produce certain products and test the effectiveness of these products.

This development research refers to the Plomp development model consisting of five development phases, namely (1) initial investigation phase, (2) design phase, (3) realization phase, (4) test, evaluation, and revision phase, and (5) phase implementation (Rochmad, 2012). In this study, development was only carried out up to the preliminary research phase, prototyping phase, and assessment phase. The assessment tools developed include model books, teacher manuals, and authentic assessment instruments and research instruments needed for the model development process. Thus, the product of this research is a book that contains an authentic assessment model of the speaking skills of elementary school students that is feasible, valid, reliable, effective, and practical along with all instruments and model development.

Data analysis to see the feasibility of an authentic assessment model of students' speaking skills. In this case, descriptive data analysis, namely the exposure of product feasibility is carried out after the value score data given by experts and educational practitioners on the feasibility of the developed product by calculating the average score. Furthermore, the criteria for evaluating the feasibility by experts and education practitioners on the authentic assessment model of students' speaking skills can be seen in the following table:

**Table of Eligibility Assessment Criteria by Experts and Practitioners
Education on Authentic Assessment Model**

Score Interval	Eligibility Criteria
3.50 – 4.00	Very Worthy
3.00 – 3.49	Worth without revision
2.50 – 2.99	Worth revising
2.00 – 2.49	Not worth revising
1.00 – 1.99	Not feasible

Model eligibility criteria
Authentic assessment of speaking skills of learning learners by education experts and practitioners is if the average score is 3.00.

Furthermore, the criteria for individual, small group, and field group trials on the model authentic assessment of students' speaking skills developed can be seen in the following table:

**Table of Assessment Criteria for Individual, Small Group and Tests
Field Group on Authentic Assessment Model**

Score Interval	Eligibility Criteria
3.50 – 4.00	Very Worthy
3.00 – 3.49	Worth without revision
2.50 – 2.99	Worth revising
2.00 – 2.49	Not worth revising
0.00 – 0.20	Not feasible

Model eligibility criteria Authentic assessment of students' speaking skills by individual trials, small group trials, and field group trials is if the average score is 3.00.

Data analysis carried out in testing the validity of the assessment instrument was carried out as follows:

- 1) The test uses a validation rater (assessor) which is quantitatively measured by finding the V index of Aiken. The formula used is

$$V = \frac{\sum s}{N(c-1)}$$

Information:

V = validity index

s = r - lo

N = rater

c = highest rating score

lo = lowest rating score

The criteria for acceptance of the validity test using the Aiken formula is if the index V is in the range 0 – 1.

- 2) Testing the validity of the students' speaking skills assessment instrument was carried out using the product-moment formula. The criteria are valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ at the real level $\alpha = 0.05$. The product-moment formulation is explained by Surapranata (2004:58) as follows:

$$r = \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Information:

rx_{xy} = correlation coefficient

N = Number of sample members

X = Total score of the questionnaire items

Y = Total score

X² = The number of squares of the questionnaire item scores

Y² = Sum of squares of total score

XY = The number of times the score of the questionnaire item with the total score

The data analysis technique used in testing the reliability of the assessment instrument is carried out as follows:

- 1) The test uses interrater validation (between raters) which is quantitatively measured using the following formula:

$$r = \frac{RJK_b - RJK_e}{RJK_b}$$

Information:

r = reliability of appraiser suitability

$$RJK_b = \frac{JK_b}{db_b}$$

$$RJK_e = \frac{JK_e}{JK_e}$$

- 2) Testing the reliability of the assessment instrument used the Cronbach Alpha formula as follows:

$$r_{11} = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum S_i^2}{S_t^2} \right)$$

Information :

r₁₁ = instrument reliability

k = number of items

Sⁱ = item variance

S^t = total variance

The criteria for testing the reliability of the assessment instrument are explained by Surapranata (2004) that an instrument is said to have reliability if the reliability coefficient is 0.70 – 0.80.

Data Analysis of the Effectiveness of the Authentic Assessment Model

Determination of the effectiveness of the authentic assessment model of students' speaking skills is seen from the achievement of learning outcomes seen from before and after the use of the authentic assessment model. Analysis of the data used is statistical testing t test with effective criteria if $t_{count} > t_{table}$ at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$.

Furthermore, to determine the effectiveness category of the authentic speaking skills assessment model, a normalized gain test (N-Gain) was carried out. N-Gain testing criteria can be seen in the table. following:

Normalized Gain Criteria Table

Score Interval	Criteria
N-Gain > 0.70	Tall
0.30 N-Gain 0.70	Currently
N-Gain < 0.30	Low

Data Analysis of the Practicality of Authentic Assessment Models.

Determination of the practicality of the authentic assessment model of students' speaking skills is seen from the consistency of the results of two measures, namely the results of expert and educational practitioners' assessments obtained from observations in the implementation of classroom assessments. The criteria for assessing the practicality of the learning model can be seen in the following table:

Table of Model Practicality Assessment Criteria

Score Interval	Criteria
3.50 – 4.00	Very Practical
3.00 – 3.49	Practical Without Repair
2.50 – 2.99	Practical Needs Repair
2.00 – 2.49	Less Practical
1.00 – 1.99	Not Practical

Model practicality criteria Authentic assessment of students' speaking skills is when the average score is 3.00.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The speaking skill assessment instrument model was developed based on the needs needed in assessing students' speaking skills so that with the availability of this assessment instrument, the competence assessment of students' speaking skills can be carried out systematically, accurately, and precisely by using the assessment aspects contained in speaking skills, namely pronunciation, volume and voice, word choice, intonation and pause, fluency and confidence. This is in line with Yusuf's (2015:35) assertion that assessment is a systematic process of gathering information including analyzing and documenting various components of education, namely context, input, process, and product without referring to value decisions. Therefore, The series of activities carried out in the development of the speaking skills assessment instrument model include the initial investigation analysis activity, the design stage, the realization stage, and the trial and revision stage. Through these activity stages, the development carried out gave birth to various tools related to the assessment of speaking skills, namely model books, teacher guidelines, and assessment instruments. The entire product of the assessment instrument model is in the form of a printed product. The development was carried out to produce a model of the assessment instrument and its equipment which was designed by following the principles of research and development research methodology. Furthermore, the developed tools were then validated by experts, namely evaluation experts, material experts, media experts, and education practitioners. The validation results show the feasibility of the product developed, then individual trials, small group trials, and large group trials are carried out, then the validity and reliability of the assessment instrument are tested and effectiveness and practicality are tested. The result is that the speaking skill assessment instrument model shows a high level of feasibility, validity, and reliability, is effective and practical to be used in assessing students' speaking competence. Regarding the criteria for this assessment instrument, it is in line with the assertion conveyed by Arikunto (2010) that an assessment instrument is said to be good if it meets the criteria, namely valid, reliable, objective, practical, and economic. Likewise, Yusuf's (2015) affirmation related to the criteria for a good instrument, namely valid, reliable,

The speaking skill assessment instrument model is equipped with devices as a support system in the implementation of speaking competency assessment as follows:

1. Model Book

The model book is a book that contains theoretical and practical guidelines for applying the model of speaking skills assessment instruments. In the model book there are sections of explanation as follows:

- a) The introduction contains an explanation related to the rationality of development and assessment.

- b) The Model Development Foundation consists of explanations related to the philosophical foundation, psychological foundation, theoretical basis, and practical basis.
- c) The development of the speaking skill assessment model consists of the development of an authentic assessment model, a speaking skill assessment model, and an assessment instrument.
- d) Guidelines for the Implementation of the Speaking Skills Assessment consist of planning the implementation of the speaking skills assessment instrument model, guidelines for the use of assessment tools, and the implementation of the assessment.

2. Teacher's Manual.

The teacher's manual is a handbook or manual that can be guided by the teacher in carrying out the assessment. This teacher manual contains an explanation of the instructions for using the teacher's manual, rationale, objectives, teacher competencies, teacher rights and obligations, teacher code of ethics, curriculum, facilities and infrastructure, assessment aspects, student characteristics, teaching materials, and speaking skills assessment instruments. learners.

3. Assessment Instruments.

The assessment instrument is an assessment sheet intended to assess the speaking competence of students. This assessment instrument contains instructions for use, statements of assessment instruments, and assessment criteria. The model set of speaking skills assessment instruments is intended to assess the speaking competence of students, in this case, the assessment is carried out directly when students display their speaking performance. The teacher acts as an assessment by referring to this developed assessment instrument sheet. The speaking skill assessment instrument model developed both model books, teacher manuals, and assessment instruments packaged in printed form is used by teachers to assess students' speaking competence, then in this case its use in schools becomes a guideline that can be used by teachers as a reference source material in assessing the competence of students' speaking skills. Percival and Ellington (1998) explained that learning resources are a set of materials or situations that are intentionally created and made to allow students to learn individually. The same thing is explained by Siregar and Nara (2010) that learning resources include everything that is used to facilitate learning. The model set of speaking skills assessment instruments developed is as a learning resource that helps teachers in assessing the competence of students' speaking skills so that the assessment of learning speaking skills can be more optimal. This is confirmed by Siregar and Nara (2010) about the benefits of learning resources, namely they can provide a more concrete and direct learning experience.

CONCLUSION:

Based on the previous discussion, it is concluded as follows:

1. The authentic assessment model developed is an assessment instrument model to assess students' speaking skills. Authentic assessment model accompaniment products are equipped with model books, teacher manuals, and assessment instruments whose feasibility has been validated by evaluation experts, material experts, linguists, and education practitioners, then individual, small group, and field group trials show that the developed product is feasible to use.
2. The results of testing the validity of the speaking skills assessment instrument using the Aiken formula and product-moment correlation show that the overall instrument item is valid.
3. The results of the reliability test of the speaking skill assessment instrument by calculating the interrater reliability coefficient (between raters) obtained the price of the reliability coefficient dance of 0.82. Furthermore, the results of the reliability test of the speaking skill assessment instrument using the Alpha Cronbach formula showed a dance reliability coefficient of 0.86. The reliability coefficients of 0.82 and 0.86 indicate high reliability, this means that the skills assessment instrument developed by the participants is reliable.
4. The authentic speaking skills assessment model that was developed proved to be effective in increasing the achievement of students' speaking skills learning outcomes with an N-Gain coefficient of 0.42 in the medium category.
5. The authentic speaking skills assessment model developed has a practicality level with a score of 2.92 in the practical category that needs improvement in the first trial and a score of 3.50 in the very practical category in the second trial.

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